

Self Development

Using text-to-speech software with a variety of texts.

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

More free features?

Help?

Simpler processes?

Voice and accent options?

Self Development

Using text-to-speech software while conducting academic internet searches.

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

More free features?

Simpler processes?

Voice and accent options?

Help?

Self Development

Using text-to-speech software while writing.

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

More free features?

Simpler processes?

Voice and accent options?

Help?

Self Development

Using text-to-speech software
with physical
documents

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

More free
features?

Help?

Simpler
processes?

Voice and accent
options?

Self Development

Using speech-to-text to assist in understanding lectures and note-taking

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

More free features?

Help?

Simpler processes?

Self Development

Using speech-to- text for writing

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

More free features?

Help?

Simpler processes?

Self Development

Using speech-to-text for personal audio memos

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

More free features?

Help?

Simpler processes?

Self Development

Using
grammar/spelling
tools alongside
text-to-speech to
compose text

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

More free
features?

Help?

Simpler
processes?

Self Development

“Training” or customizing spelling/grammar tools

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

More free
features?

Help?

Simpler
processes?

Self Development

Using Word read-aloud to check writing: use the read aloud function to catch spelling errors when there were correctly spelled words that weren't the intended word.

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Simpler processes?

Help?

Self Development

Changing font size, style and colour

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Help?

Self Development

Finding visual content while reading to gain knowledge about a topic before returning to the assigned reading.

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

More integrated features like images?

Help?

